

Semantic Representation Challenges in AAS, ECLASS and SAMM

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Asset Administration Shell (AAS)

Asset Administration Shell

We need a standard way to model products, industrial assets, ...

Everyone creates their own ontology, have their own API structure, and their own structure and exchange format → hard to generalize

- AAS as an International Electrotechnical Commission standard: IEC 63278
- Standardized Digital Twin with common structure
- Reusable models as a form of **Submodel Templates** created To cover common use cases (asset location, digital nameplate, handover documents, carbon footprint, ...)
- Standard REST API to access/manipulate model structure and content
- Semantics rely on links to external dictionaries like IEC61360 such as ECLASS, IEC CDD, ...
- AASX as a self-contained file format for data exchange

Part 1: Metamodel

Part 2: Application Programming Interfaces

Part 3a: Data Specification – IEC 61360

Part 5: Package File Format (AASX)

Why Asset Administration Shell?

- Ecodesign for Sustainable Products Regulation (ESPR) → Battery Passport, Digital Product Passport, ...
- Manufacturing as a Service, Plug and Produce, ...
- More than 100+ IDTA members and already adopted by many manufacturers (STAHL, Wago, ABB, ..)
- Open-Source tooling (Eclipse Digital Twin project)
 - [Eclipse AASX Package Explorer](#) - Visual editor
 - [Eclipse BaSyx](#) and [Eclipse FA³ST](#) - Hosting instances (hosting digital twin) and connect to OPC UA/MQTT/...
 - [Eclipse Mnestic](#) - Web Application UI (view only)
 - [Aas-core-works](#) - Stable SDKs in various programming languages Java, Python, C++, C#, Rust

STAHL DIGITAL TWIN WELCOME

LOGIN

CLOSE AAS

SEARCH: IS1+ Remote I/O CPU module For Zone 1

SERIAL NR. 10003506595 ART. NR. 279953

NAMEPLATE	TECHNICAL DATA	DOCUMENTATION	CONTACT INFORMATION
Manufacturer product designation IS1+ Remote I/O CPU module For Zone 1	Manufacturer Name R. STAHL Schaltgeräte GmbH	Manufacturer product code 9442/32-10-00 CPU	Manufacturer product root Modules and components for IS1
product article number of manufacturer 279953	Manufacturer order code 9442/32-10-00 CPU	Manufacturer product root Modules and components for IS1	
Serial number 10003506595	Date of manufacture 2023-09-01	Hardware Version 1.08	
Software Version 1.2	Firmware Version 1.01		

<https://dt.r-stahl.com/>

Battery Product Passport

Battery ID: IMR18650V1

GENERAL	PERFORMANCE	HEALTH	SUSTAINABILITY
Type Lithium-Manganese-Oxide (LMO)	Rated Capacity 94 kWh	State of Health (SoH) 20%	Ni 47% Co 9% Li 19%
Model Pi4 Orionis	Original Power -1.7976931348623157e+308 kW	Charging Cycles 0%	Pb 0%

GENERAL INFORMATION	PRODUCT CONDITION	COMPONENTS	BATTERY COMPOSITION	CELL CHEMISTRY	ELECTROCHEMICAL PROPERTIES	ADDITIONAL INFORMATION	DATA EXCHANGE INFORMATION		
Battery ID (DMC) IMR18650V1	Date of Manufacture 2022-01-24	Manufacturer Information CompanyE 6S-250E CityE Germany	Battery Type Lithium-Manganese-Oxide (LMO)	Place of Manufacturing CityE	Manufacturer Contact +49 89 1234567893 https://www.CompanyE.com companyE@company.com	Dimensions of the battery L: 2000mm, H: 200mm, W: 1000mm	Weight 3500 kg	Date of placing on the market 27.04.2022	CO2-Footprint 210 CO2e/kWh

<https://github.com/eclipse-tractusx/digital-product-pass>

Why RDF and SPARQL?

- RDF: enables easy data integration into a uniform representation (knowledge graph)
- SPARQL: enables complex queries on distributed AAS shells/submodels in combination with other data sources, like
 - Aggregate the carbon footprint for all my products in a particular category.
 - Aggregate the carbon footprint for an assembly.
 - Find a specific component for a new design using nameplate and technical data.
 - Extract properties of all nameplate submodels from an endpoint:

```
prefix aas: <https://admin-shell.io/aas/3/0/>
```

```
select ?sm ?element ?p ?o {  
  service <aas-api:https://v3.admin-shell.io.com> {  
    <aas-api:endpoint> <aas-api:shells> ?shell .  
    ?shell aas:submodels [ <aas-api:resolved> ?sm ] . ?sm aas:semanticId ?semId . ?semId aas:keys ?key .  
    ?key aas:value "https://admin-shell.io/zvei/nameplate/1/0/Nameplate" .  
    ?sm (!<:>)+ ?element .  
    { ?element a aas:Property } union { ?element a aas:MultiLanguageProperty }  
    ?element ?p ?o .  
  }  
}
```

AAS RDF

```
{
  "idShort": "Nameplate",
  "id": "https://aas.company.com/1873",
  "submodelElements": [
    {
      "idShort": "ManufacturerName",
      "semanticId": {
        "type": "ExternalReference",
        "keys": [
          {
            "type": "GlobalReference",
            "value": "0173-1#02-AA0677#004"
          }
        ]
      },
      "value": [
        {
          "language": "de",
          "text": "Kühle Hersteller"
        },
        {
          "language": "en",
          "text": "Cool Manufacturer"
        }
      ],
      "modelType": "MultiLanguageProperty"
    },
    {
      "modelType": "Submodel"
    }
  ]
}
```

```
1 @prefix aas: <https://admin-shell.io/aas/3/0/> .
2 @prefix aas-hassemantics: <https://admin-shell.io/aas/3/0/HasSemantics/> .
3 @prefix aas-identifiable: <https://admin-shell.io/aas/3/0/Identifiable/> .
4 @prefix aas-key: <https://admin-shell.io/aas/3/0/Key/> .
5 @prefix aas-keytypes: <https://admin-shell.io/aas/3/0/KeyTypes/> .
6 @prefix aas-langstring: <https://admin-shell.io/aas/3/0/AbstractLangString/> .
7 @prefix aas-mlp: <https://admin-shell.io/aas/3/0/MultiLanguageProperty/> .
8 @prefix aas-referable: <https://admin-shell.io/aas/3/0/Referable/> .
9 @prefix aas-reference: <https://admin-shell.io/aas/3/0/Reference/> .
10 @prefix aas-referencetypes: <https://admin-shell.io/aas/3/0/ReferenceTypes/> .
11 @prefix aas-submodel: <https://admin-shell.io/aas/3/0/Submodel/> .
12 @prefix xsd: <http://www.w3.org/2001/XMLSchema#> .
13
14 <https://aas.company.com/1873> a aas:Submodel ;
15   aas-identifiable:id "https://aas.company.com/1873" ;
16   aas-referable:idShort "Nameplate" ;
17   aas-submodel:submodelElements <https://aas.company.com/1873/submodel-elements/ManufacturerName> .
18
19 <https://aas.company.com/1873/submodel-elements/ManufacturerName> a aas:MultiLanguageProperty ;
20   aas-referable:idShort "ManufacturerName" ;
21   aas-hassemantics:semanticId [
22     a aas:Reference ;
23     aas-reference:keys
24       [ a aas:Key ;
25         aas-key:type aas-keytypes:GlobalReference ;
26         aas-key:value "0173-1#02-AA0677#004" ;
27       ] ;
28     aas-reference:type aas-referencetypes:ExternalReference
29   ] ;
30   aas-mlp:value
31     [ a aas:LangStringTextType ;
32       aas-langstring:language "de" ;
33       aas-langstring:text "Kühle Hersteller"
34     ],
35     [ a aas:LangStringTextType ;
36       aas-langstring:language "en" ;
37       aas-langstring:text "Cool Manufacturer"
38     ] .
```


Observations Regarding Current RDF Serialization

- Property URLs extend class URLs: <https://admin-shell.io/aas/3/0/Identifiable/id>
 - Makes it unnecessarily hard to write AAS-RDF (too many prefixes)
 - Neither the JSON nor the XML serialization use class-prefixes in properties
- Revision number in namespace: <https://admin-shell.io/aas/3/1/Identifiable/id>
- Naming of RDF elements is not specified
- Ordered lists ([SubmodelElementList](#)) and collections are not properly represented in RDF
- No usage of [rdf:langString](#) and [XSD](#) datatypes (everything is string!)
- We should work on an RDF-native interpretation/profile:
[aas-specs/issues/384](#)
- First steps are taken in the IDTA Ontologies workstream (Semantics WG)

ECLASS Product Classification

ECLASS, IEC CDD, use in AAS

- ECLASS is:
 - comprehensive product type classification (in particular of electrical and electronic components)
 - data dictionary for describing product properties
 - foundation for interoperable vendor product catalogs
- Based on the "OntoML" ISO 13584-32 standard
- Same structure as IEC 61360 [Common Data Dictionary \(CDD\)](#)
- Widely used in AAS to provide shared "semantics" of product properties
- Also used in OPC UA, Automation ML, etc

Comparison of fundamental structures for the two master data dictionaries IEC CDD and eCl@ss

IEC CDD (maintained by IEC/SC 3D)

- + Information-model according to IEC 61360
- + Class tree is structured by standards
- + Unlimited class levels; 1st level class is called domain
- + Classification by SDOs based on international (ISO or IEC) standards → Responsible: TCs/SCs
- + Share common aspects/features within IEC 61360-4

eCl@ss (maintained by eCl@ss e.V.)

- + Information-model according to ISO 13584-42
- + Class tree is structured by technical areas
- + 4 class levels: 3 classification classes + application class
- + Classification by EG (Expert Groups) based on consortia standards → Responsible: EGs
- + eCl@ss BASIC not appropriate for reference repository

ECLASS Development

ECLASS ContentDevelopmentPlatform

en eptos™ - ECLASS ContentDevelopmentPlatform Prod

Select entity

English ECLASS11.1 Application class lamp

Anchor Refresh Collapse all List view

Favorites

- Search in ECLASS
- Content Manager**
- My change request
- Classification class
- Application class
- Aspect
- Block
- Property**
- Browse
- Move
- Join
- Transform
- Value list
- Value
- Keyword
- Synonym
- Constraint
- My tasks
- Reports

Change Request Manager

- Import
- Reports

Template Manager

General

- Search in ECLASS
- User profile

Info

21-04-12 Packing tool
21-04-13 Labeling tool
21-04-14 Height adjustment device
21-04-15 Puller tool, extractor tool
21-04-17 Clamping tool
21-04-17-01 Door clamp
Door clamp
Door clamp
Add on Documentation
Commercial
Customs tariff number
Customs tariff number
Regional customs tariff number
Country of customs tariff number
Type of customs tariff number
Use of customs tariff number
Customs tariff number
customs tariff number (TARIC)
HS-Code of the WCO
Used property simulation
number of customs tariff numbers
Used property simulation
Identification
Manufacturer
Supplier
Used property simulation
Information
Clamp height
Clamp width
Span
Weight
rail tread
Used property simulation

Results: [286]

Property 0173-1#02-AAO677#002 - Manufacturer name

Export Create Change text Delete Reactivate Replace Clone Copy Assign Withdraw Add to

Overview General Admin Format Attribute Change request History Values Release Alternate units Cons

Preferred name	Manufacturer name
IRDI	0173-1#02-AAO677#002
Abstract property	false
Definition	legally valid designation of the natural or judicial person which is directly responsible for into circulation
Remark	Preliminary establishment of the designation of the manufacturer subject to changes by f
Type of property	Non-dependent
Valency type	Multivalent
Definition class	ECLASS (0173-1#01-RAA001#001)
Property data type	String
Class type code	A21 - Organization
Date of creation	11.02.2011
Version date	30.01.2017
Creator	

- Comprehensive Content Development Platform
- 29 languages (complete translations)
- Continuous development, now ECLASS version 15
- Added in **last year**: 490 classes, 810 properties, 1700 values, 210 value lists

ECLASS Semantic Representation

ECLASS has worked on semantic representation for 4 years. Serialization as RDF:

- [Part 1: Base Model & ECLASS Content](#), ECLASS Technical Specification 110, 2024-04-22.
- Part 2: ECLASS Validation with SHACL & SPARQL (in review)
- Part 3: ECLASS RDF Usage (pending)
 - Part 3.a: RDF product description based on ECLASS
 - Part 3.b: Usage of ECLASS RDF in W3C Web of Things (WoT) Thing Description
 - Part 3.c: Usage of ECLASS RDF in AAS. Older paper can serve as insight: [Modelling the Semantics of Data of an Asset Administration Shell with Elements of ECLASS](#) V. 1.0, 2021-06-29

ECLASS RDF

```
<ontoml:property xsi:type="ontoml:NON_DEPENDENT_P_DET_Type" id="0173-1#02-BAD046#009" guid="f141e2b76ca44965994f"
<name_scope class_ref="0173-1#01-RAA001#001"/>
<date_of_original_definition>2004-09-27Z</date_of_original_definition>
<date_of_current_version>2024-10-06Z</date_of_current_version>
<date_of_current_revision>2024-10-06Z</date_of_current_revision>
<revision>1</revision>
<status>66</status>
<source_language language_code="en" country_code="US"/>
<preferred_name>
  <label language_code="en" country_code="US" translation_quality_level="Non-Native">Max. delay time with chan
</preferred_name>
<synonymous_names>
  <label id="0173-1#Z6-ACD190#001" language_code="en" country_code="US">delay time with change of signal, max<
</synonymous_names>
<definition>
  <text language_code="en" country_code="US" translation_quality_level="Non-Native">Maximum required time at c
</definition>
<domain xsi:type="ontoml:REAL_MEASURE_TYPE_Type">
  <unit unit_ref="0173-1#05-AAA114#005"/>
  <quantity quantity_ref="0173-1#Z4-BAJ217#005"/>
</domain>
<is_multivalent>true</is_multivalent>
</ontoml:property>
```

```
1 v eclass15-0:0173-1-02-BAD046-009
```

```
2   rdf:type          owl:ObjectProperty;
3   rdfs:comment      "Maximum required time at change of signal between when a required function is triggered and when execution of it is completed"@en;
4   rdfs:label        "Max. delay time with change of signal"@en;
5   rdfs:range        iec61360:RealMeasureType;
6   rdfs:subPropertyOf eclass:nonDependent;
7   eclass:IRDI       "0173-1#02-BAD046#009";
8   eclass:hasQuantity eclass15-0:0173-1-Z4-BAJ217-005;
9   eclass:hasUnit     eclass15-0:0173-1-05-AAA114-005;
10  eclass:multivalent true;
11  eclass:synonym     "delay time with change of signal, max"@en .
```

7.3.1 Property with Unit

```
eclass13-0:0173-1-02-BAD046-007
  rdf:type owl:ObjectProperty ;
  rdfs:comment "Maximum required time at change of signal between
function is triggered and when execution of it is completed"@en ;
  rdfs:label "Max. delay time with change of signal"@en ;
  rdfs:range iec61360:RealMeasureType ;
  rdfs:subPropertyOf eclass:nonDependent ;
  eclass:IRDI "0173-1#02-BAD046#007" ;
  eclass:hasQuantity eclass13-0:0173-1-Z4-BAJ217-003 ;
  eclass:hasUnit eclass13-0:0173-1-05-AAA114-003 ;
  eclass:multivalent "true"^^xsd:boolean ;
  eclass:synonym "delay time with change of signal, max"@en ;
.
#unit
eclass13-0:0173-1-05-AAA114-003
  rdf:type eclass:Unit ;
  rdfs:comment "0,001-fold of the SI base unit second"@en ;
  rdfs:label "millisecond"@en ;
  eclass:IRDI "0173-1#05-AAA114#003" ;
  eclass:float64Conversion eclass13-0:AAA114-to-AAA203 ;
  eclass:float64Conversion eclass13-0:AAA114-to-AAA452 ;
  eclass:hasAoC eclass13-0:0173-1-Z2-AAA168-001 ;
  eclass:shortName "ms"@en ;
.
#Aspect of conversion
eclass13-0:0173-1-Z2-AAA168-001
```

ECLASS in AAS

```
18
19 <https://aas.company.com/1873/submodel-elements/ManufacturerName> a aas:MultiLanguageProperty ;
20   aas-referable:idShort "ManufacturerName" ;
21   aas-hassemantics:semanticId [
22     | a aas:Reference ;
23     | aas-reference:keys
24       [ a aas:Key ;
25         | aas-key:type aas-keytypes:GlobalReference ;
26         | aas-key:value "0173-1#02-AA0677#004" ;
27       ] ;
28     | aas-reference:type aas-referencetypes:ExternalReference
29   ] ;
30   aas-mlp:value
31     [ a aas:LangStringTextType ;
32       | aas-langstring:language "de" ;
33       | aas-langstring:text "Kühle Hersteller"
34     ],
35     [ a aas:LangStringTextType ;
36       | aas-langstring:language "en" ;
37       | aas-langstring:text "Cool Manufacturer"
38     ] .
```

- ECLASS properties are used in AAS by copying IRDI & name
- Involving a lot of intermediate blank nodes
- Encoded as String not a direct link to the resource
- Redundant and inefficient representation
- Quite difficult to query

General Challenges (innate, harder to fix)

4 years ago we participated in the ECLASS Semantics WG (Alexiev, V. ECLASS RDF Representation. Dec 2020. [HTML](#), [slides](#), [link](#))

- Comprehensive comparison of ECLASS to product representation approaches **grounded in real-world objects**
 - E.g. Schema.org product classes and GS1 WebVoc
- Modeling methodology (OntoML) doesn't promote "**Ontological realism**"
 - Instead of product parts, documents, organizations etc., it talks about blocks, aspects, polymorphism, cardinalities
- Properties are grouped by "blocks" and "aspects" not **real-world things**
 - E.g. Manufacturer Aspect includes attributes like Manufacturer Name and SKU
 - However, these belong to two different objects: Organization vs Product Model
 - Makes it harder to reuse external LOD, e.g. a KG of Companies: in such case Manufacturer Name would also be repeated redundantly at the product level
- Class and property URLs are **unstable** at 2 levels:
 - ECLASS namespace has the release number
 - Each term uses a versioned IRDI (the last part is a counter)

Specific Challenges (easier to fix)

AAS issue ECLASS RDF Representation [#422](#), includes diagram

- All props are ObjectProps, and a lot of them go through a "parasitic" node (eg **iec61360:IntType**) before they reach the literal **iec61360:value**
- **subPropertyOf** is used as a mere hierarchical organization device rather than with its proper semantics of inferring new triples
- **subClassOf** is also used as an organizational device, and the inferences of this are not taken into account
- Blocks (groups of properties) are subClassOf **iec61360:ClassReferenceType**, which itself is subClassOf **iec61360:DataType** ?
- Properties have **rdfs:range** but not **rdfs:domain** (instead **eclass:isDescribedBy** is used)
- Property cardinality is indicated with **eclass:multivalent** (boolean) instead of being **owl:FunctionalProperty** (when single-valent)
- Could reuse an established units ontology like QUDT units and quantityKinds rather than its own weird treatment: **eclass:AoC** "AspectOfConversion" with
 - Strange exponentByte (can there be Byte squared or Byte reciprocal?)
 - Not documented in RDF: exponentE, exponentDec, exponentSh, etc

Eclipse Semantic Modeling Framework (ESMF)
and Semantic Aspect Meta Model (SAMM)

AAS Schemas and Machine-Readability

- Early AAS schemas (submodels) were PDFs
- Now submodels are defined using AAS Submodel Templates (see the [IDTA catalog of Submodels](#))
 - Machine-processable documentation using AsciiDoc and Antora
 - Smart standards communities also use plain text and these tools through Metanorma
 - [AAS Core Specification also switched to plain text](#), which is positive
- But the template approach:
 - Is based on prototypes/examples
 - Does not constitute a strict schema with defined property cardinalities, ranges, etc
- ESMF and SAMM try to fill this gap
- AAS and ESMF are part of the Eclipse Digital Twin programme

ESMF/SAMM as a Polyglot Modeling Framework

- SAMM is part of ESMF and is used for creating digital twin models.
 - Originated from OpenManufacturingPlatform (Bosch, ...)
 - Widely used in Catena-X, now in Manufacturing-X, Factory-X...
- SAMM covers usual IoT affordances/capabilities (Property, Operation, Event)
 - Known from other frameworks like Web of Things (WoT)
- ESMF provides tooling for generating machine-readable artefacts:
 - Documentation, OpenAPI specs, JSON Schemas, etc
- **Polyglot Modeling** approach: single master schema, with generators for various technical artefacts
 - [YAML LD issue #19](#) lists about 15 frameworks that do similar tasks
 - **LinkML** (originated as BioLinkML) is the most accomplished framework: it has the most features (e.g. binary arrays) and generators
 - LinkML uses YAML and authoring is simpler, SAMM uses Turtle and feels a bit like writing assembler (same level as SHACL)

```

@prefix samm: <urn:samm:org.eclipse.esmf:meta-model:2.1.0#> .
@prefix xsd: <http://www.w3.org/2001/XMLSchema#> .
@prefix : <urn:samm:org.eclipse.esmf:1.0.0#> .
@prefix samm-u: <urn:samm:org.eclipse.esmf.samm:unit:2.1.0#> .

:Product a samm:Aspect ;
  samm:description "Simple representation of a product"@en ;
  samm:properties ( :productionDate [ samm:property :manufacturer; samm:optional true ] :name ) ;
  samm:operations ( ) ;
  samm:events ( ) .

:productionDate a samm:Property ;
  samm:characteristic :Characteristic1 ;
  samm:exampleValue "2024-10-12"^^xsd:date .

:manufacturer a samm:Property ;
  samm:preferredName "Manufacturer"@en ;
  samm:characteristic :Characteristic2 ;
  samm:exampleValue "Cool Manufacturer" .

:name a samm:Property ;
  samm:preferredName "Name"@en ;
  samm:description "Name of the product"@en ;
  samm:characteristic :Characteristic3 ;
  samm:exampleValue "Cool Product Name" .

:Characteristic1 a samm:Characteristic ;
  samm:dataType xsd:date .

:Characteristic2 a samm:Characteristic ;
  samm:dataType xsd:string .

:Characteristic3 a samm:Characteristic ;
  samm:dataType xsd:string .

```

- Visual Aspect Model Editor
[eclipse-esmf/esmf-aspect-model-editor](https://github.com/eclipse-esmf/esmf-aspect-model-editor)
- More advanced examples in the context of automotive (Catena-X): [eclipse-tractusx/sldt-semantic-models](https://github.com/eclipse-tractusx/sldt-semantic-models)

The screenshot displays the Aspect Model Editor (AMM) interface. On the left, a code editor shows the SAMM code for a 'Product' aspect and its associated properties and characteristics. The right side of the interface shows a graphical model diagram. The 'Product' entity is represented by a blue box with a description. It has three properties: 'productionDate', 'manufacturer', and 'name'. Each property is associated with a characteristic: 'productionDate' with 'Characteristic1', 'manufacturer' with 'Characteristic2', and 'name' with 'Characteristic3'. The interface includes a menu with options like 'HTML Documentation', 'OpenAPI Specification', and 'JSON Schema', and a sidebar with a legend for SAMM elements.

SAMM vs Semantic Modeling and Ontologies

SAMM uses RDF and SHACL to define IoT models, but semantics is used only as a means and not as end-goal.

- Long-established semantic modeling practices (RDFS, OWL) are not followed
- Usage of Blank Nodes forced! (**samm:Property**)
- Aspect properties are enumerated in explicit rdf:Lists, enforcing closed-world interpretation, preventing future extension
- Product/machine properties are modeled with classes (**samm:Aspect**, **samm:Property**; similar to ECLASS Aspects), rather than straight RDF properties
- URN-based naming scheme (similar to Microsoft Azure DTDL naming schemes), prevents semantic resolution and reuse of existing ontologies
- Reuse of existing ontologies and extensions is prohibited (see SAAM [Architectural Decision Records](#)). Re-inventing unit catalog

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References

- Alexiev, V. ECLASS RDF Representation. Dec 2020. [HTML](#), [slides](#), [link](#)
- [ECLASS Technical Specification 110: ECLASS Serialization as RDF. Part 1](#), Version 1.0.0. Apr 2024.
- Eclipse Foundation. [Eclipse Semantic Modeling Framework Documentation](#). Accessed December 9, 2024.
- Rimaz, M.H., Plociennik, C., Kunz, L. and Ruskowski, M., 2023, September. Am I in Good Shape? Flexible Way to Validate Asset Administration Shell Data Entry via Shapes Constraint Language. In 2023 IEEE 28th International Conference on Emerging Technologies and Factory Automation (ETFA) (pp. 1-6). IEEE.
- Rimaz, M.H., Plociennik, and Ruskowski, M., Semantic Asset Administration Shell for Circular Economy. In Proceedings of the The 2nd International Workshop on Knowledge Graphs for Sustainability (KG4S 2024) co-located with the 21st Extended Semantic Web Conference (ESWC 2024). Sep 2024. [CEUR Vol 3753](#)
- Rimaz, M.H. (2024). [Semantic Asset Administration Shell for Circular Economy](#), Master Thesis. University of Kaiserslautern-Landau. Jan 2024. DOI 10.13140/RG.2.2.33957.10729.

Thank You

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